

RCD Nexus Day 2025 Final Report

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Event Overview

With generous support from Internet2 and the National Science Foundation, the RCD Nexus Day 2025 was held on July 20, 2025 in Columbus, OH, as an official co-located event of the PEARC25. RCD Nexus Day hosted a total of 121 attendees from 78 institutions, including twenty-one (21) from non-R1 higher education institutions, eleven (11) from non-higher education organizations, sixteen (16) from [EPSCoR](#) jurisdictions, fourteen (14) from Hispanic Serving Institutions, six (6) from Historically Black Colleges and Universities, one (1) from a Tribal College, and seven (7) from another type of Minority Serving Institution. Twelve (12) attendees received travel grants that allowed them to attend not only RCD Nexus Day, but also the entire PEARC25 conference, with preference given to attendees from the categories listed

above. Dana Brunson of Internet2, along with Daphne McCanse and Karen Garrett of Internet2 (contract) served as general workshop organizers. The day began with a short general session before dividing into the two workshops described in detail below.

Workshop 1: Future Creating Workshop

Workshop Goals and Overview

The purpose of this interactive workshop was to engage and empower cyberinfrastructure professionals as they identify workforce development (professional training) challenges and create opportunities for the community to develop resources to address the needs. In this workshop, participants were led by Betsy Hillery, Winona Snapp-Childs, Michael Weiner, Michael Navicky and Timothy Middelkoop through three phases: identifying barriers, envisioning ideal futures, and developing actionable solutions for RCD professional development. Organized into cohorts based on professional experience (early, mid, and late career) and also focus (data-facing, system-facing, researcher-facing, strategy/policy professionals, and emerging centers), the group arrived at concrete recommendations tailored to different career stages. Future directions include evaluating which resources can be prioritized for the community-based development of resources for early-career professionals and, thus, strengthening the national RCD community.

This workshop hosted 94 attendees from 53 institutions, including sixteen (16) from non-R1 higher education institutions, five (5) from non-higher education organizations, ten (10) from [EPSCoR](#) jurisdictions, ten (10) from Hispanic Serving Institutions, two (2) from Historically Black Colleges and Universities, one (1) from a Tribal College, and four (4) from another type of Minority Serving Institution.

Breakout 1: Identify Key Challenges, Gaps and Training Needs.

In this phase of the workshop, the *critique* phase, participants identified current problems and issues as regards training for cyberinfrastructure professionals.

Key takeaways: The top identified challenges or gaps were 1) Centralized community repository of documentation and knowledge (knowledge base); 2) Navigating institutional culture Resources for regional/local organizational community building; 3) Curriculum for behavioral competencies.

Session Facilitator: Timothy Middelkoop

1. Participants identified strong demand for:

- HPC fundamentals (e.g., SLURM, cluster setup, schedulers).
- AI & GPU computing (workflows, acceleration, containerization).
- Software & systems skills (Docker, Python, MPI, HTCondor, Warewulf).
- Cyberinfrastructure knowledge (storage, networking, compliance).
- Security & strategic thinking (cybersecurity, systems thinking, decision-making).

2. Professional Development Needs

- Communication & facilitation: Presenting across domains, customer service, bridging IT-researcher gaps.
- Mentorship & leadership: Structured mentoring, feedback loops, strategic outreach.
- Time management: Balancing training with operational demands.
- Grant writing & outreach: Proposal development and promoting RCD services.

3. Structural & Contextual Needs

- Onboarding & career mapping: SOPs, skill maps, structured pathways.
- Documentation & resource awareness: Navigating centralized knowledge bases.
- Institutional navigation: Adapting to leadership changes and organizational culture.
- Training formats: Preference for hands-on, shadowing, self-paced, and experiential learning.

4. Common Challenges & Barriers

- Knowledge gaps: Limited exposure to emerging tech, lack of structured onboarding, difficulty translating general resources to CI-specific contexts.
- Time & resource constraints: Limited time, staffing, funding, and sandbox environments.
- Training access issues: Mismatched training levels, outdated documentation, lack of mentorship.
- Institutional challenges: Siloing, disconnect between IT and leadership, low faculty awareness of RCD services.
- Soft skills gaps: Advocacy, terminology, strategic communication, and project management.

Breakout 2: Visioning and Solutions.

In this phase of the workshop, the *utopian* phase, participants identified imaginative ideas for an ideal future. Workshop facilitators were

Key takeaways: The top ideas for an ideal (training) future included 1) a web-based RCD resource catalog that has the following attributes: FAIR, community-based, metadata requirements, open submission process, review process (with reviews having experience level and facings identified), and issue tracking.

Session facilitator: Mike Navicky

1. Onboarding & Orientation

- Meet team members and understand management structure.
- Distribute SOPs and onboarding roadmaps.
- Learn institutional context, goals, and researcher landscape 1.

2. Foundational Technical Training

- Introduction to research computing hardware and software.
- Walkthroughs of HPC components and philosophies.
- Hands-on cluster building (bare metal or VM).
- Use of sandbox environments for experimentation.

3. Soft Skills & Communication

- Customer service and researcher engagement training.

- Communication styles and active listening.
 - Presentation skills for diverse audiences (IT, leadership, researchers).
 - Marketing and outreach to promote RCD services.
4. Mentorship & Peer Learning
 - Find mentors or advocates within and outside the institution.
 - Shadowing/apprenticeship with experienced staff.
 - Peer cohorts and community engagement (e.g., CaRCC, Campus Champions).
 5. Documentation & Knowledge Sharing
 - Improve and adapt internal documentation.
 - Maintain personal and institutional knowledge bases.
 - Encourage publishable internal documentation.
 6. Specialized & Continuous Learning
 - Sabbatical training and work exchange programs.
 - Continuous training via external platforms (e.g., Carpentries, OU Virtual Residency, NVIDIA DLI).
 - Self-directed learning and exploration encouraged.
 7. Strategic & Leadership Development
 - Training on decision-making, systems thinking, and strategic planning.
 - Understanding institutional culture and navigating leadership dynamics.
 - Behavioral competencies and experiential learning emphasized.

Breakout 3: Identify Most-Needed Resources.

In this phase of the workshop, the *realization* phase, participants identified concrete tasks for action to move toward the utopian vision while keeping in mind the constraints identified through the critique.

Key takeaways. Participants identified the most-needed resources to be (1) a centralized repository of documentation and knowledge; (2) a guide to navigating institutional culture; and (3) a curriculum for behavioral competencies.

Session facilitator: Michael Weiner

1. Training Resources That Exist
 - Carpentries & OU Virtual Residency: Frequently cited for foundational and instructor training.
 - NVIDIA Deep Learning Institute: Used for cloud and AI-related training.
 - Cornell Virtual Workshop & SDSC COMPLECS: Noted for continuing education.
 - LCI (Linux Clusters Institute): Recognized for hardware and cluster-building training.
 - GitHub, Docker, and software documentation: Mentioned as practical tools needing better onboarding support.
2. Training Gaps Identified
 - Sabbatical Training & Work Exchange Programs: No national programs exist.
 - Facilitation Frameworks for Intake Interviews: Lacking structured training.
 - Behavioral Competency Curriculum: Missing across strategy/policy-facing roles.

- Institution-Specific Onboarding: Often informal or nonexistent.
- Troubleshooting Manuals for Systems-Facing Roles: No centralized resource.
- Mentorship Frameworks: Need for structured local mentoring programs.

3. Innovative Suggestions

- Create a centralized web portal with metadata tagging and peer review.
- Develop Canvas-like tools for onboarding and training walkthroughs.
- Use social media and short videos for outreach and community building.
- Encourage shadowing/apprenticeship models and sandbox environments.
- Promote collaboration with vendors and resource providers (e.g., Jetstream2, FABRIC).
- Establish metrics for success (badging, certifications, follow-up reports).

Table Report Outs: Recommendations from each table, and the number of votes each received from all participants in attendance

Table	Topic	Count
2	Customer Service Training	5
2	Change Management Training	6
3	Semi annual working groups to discuss results of workshop and what action items need to be assigned	2
3	Leveraging existing community resources (Jetstream2 / FABRIC) to meet needs for a community test bed.	4
4	Facilitation Framework and training for research intake interviews	1
4	Cultivating Creativity and Curiosity in Research Computing Facilitation or among innovate thinking among CI facilitation	7
5	Guidelines and best practices for effective internal resources facing documentation	0
5	How to develop a researcher database	0
6	Resources for getting to know your own regional/local peers and researcher audiences, collaborations, clientele skills	3
6	Resources for regional/location organizational community building	8
7	Hands on exposure with a mentor on representative resources	5
7	Centralized community repository of documentation and knowledge	15
8	Low cost HPC Admin Training	8
8	Test/Dev HPC environment for learning HPC Technologies	6

9	Institution Specific Training	0
9	Shadowing people who do similar jobs outside of their institution	5
10	Curriculum for Behavior Competencies	10
10	Navigating your own institutional culture	14

Breakout 4: Workshop Reflection and Ideas for the Future

In the last session of the workshop, participants reflected on the workshop format and suggested plans for creating and maintaining community resources.

Key takeaways. Participants prioritized making the RCD professional development resource catalog a FAIR open source community project, with processes for updates via git issues and a searchable web portal interface with metadata. They recommended curation of documentation and resources with an emphasis that peer review comes from all levels of experience. Finally, a system for sabbatical training at other institutions, or a work exchange program, was recommended.

Session facilitator: Betsy Hillery

Table Report Outs: Recommendations from each table, and the number of votes each received from all participants in attendance

Table	Topic	Count
2	Web Portal, searchable, with metadata for catalog	11
2	Include professional development training at a yearly update event	7
3	1-2 week summer school focus on what they will be working with provided by a central collaborative entity	3
3	Sabbatical training larger in career and work exchange program	11
4	Develop open community platforms for post PEARC attendance engagement utilization of RCN for grant funded activities	3
4	Collaborating with resource providers and vendors (profit/nonprofit) for training purposes and speaker engagement	4
5	Use gen AI to distill contributions from all the teams in real time into 2-3 outcomes of the breakout goals.	1

5	Feed the same data into different open sources LLMS to variations of the comes. Split the table into two groups - 1 rotate through the tables to suggest new ideas and offer different perspectives. The other group stays at the table to "defend" their idea.	1
6	Incentivize reviewing and maintaining the RCD resource catalog with small travel grants	1
6	Make RCD resource catalog a FAIR open source community project with process and issue training (github)	14
7	Curation of documentation and resources with an emphasis that peer review comes from all levels of experience	12
7	Local/Regional groups aggregated under CarCC to have semi-regular discussion and working sessions, with annual or biannual meetups to pull them together.	7
8	Wiki of HPC admin documentation and training administered by CarCC	6
8	Track progress of previous initiatives at this meeting don't reinvent the wheel.	0
9	CaRCC carpentries - repo and voting and volunteering platform for training material and sessions (popular ideas get more updates)	8
9	Knowledge matrix - how to convince your boss to let you participate in national/volunteer activities (e.g. trainings) based on traits of your boss.	6
10	Catalog website ongoing submissions ideas - review on a regular basis by a committee of 3 -6 people	0
10	Build a strong formal relations between CaRCC and CASC	0

Recommendations and Next Steps

This successful workshop generated many ideas about how to support early- to late-career cyberinfrastructure professionals from a variety of roles. Many of the ideas bridging the gaps/needs and ideal future session focused on curating and augmenting existing resources rather than creating new resources. We recommend that the information from this workshop be further evaluated within a community context.

Workshop 2: Refreshing and Refining the CaRCC Capabilities Model Questions

This workshop hosted twenty-seven (27) attendees from 25 institutions, including five (5) from non-R1 higher education institutions, six (6) from non-higher education organizations, six (6) from [EPSCoR](#) jurisdictions, four (4) from Hispanic Serving Institutions, four (4) from Historically Black Colleges and Universities, and three (3) from another type of Minority Serving Institution.

Workshop Goals and Overview

Following the adoption and implementation of the CaRCC Capabilities Model by at least 75 institutions since its 2020 inception, the Capabilities Model working group has received a variety of feedback. While responses to this feedback have been implemented in the model's online portal, data visualization and benchmarking tools, and other usability enhancements, a variety of feedback has pertained to the content of the questions in the Model, and in light of changes in the RCD service landscape. Thus, this workshop was executed to review and refresh the set of questions in the Model, leveraging a series of breakout discussions to crowdsource community feedback on specific questions, within the categorical 'facings' and (sub)topics of capabilities, and across the entire model and usability components.

To ensure maximal and efficient contributions during the workshop, participants and other already-engaged community members were invited to attend one of three preparatory sessions, during which the impetus, history, content organization, and community engagement with the model were presented, as well as the workshop objectives and structure. Prep session participants were asked to complete a review of the questions in personalized documents that could be referenced during the in-person workshop. In these documents and during the workshops, participants were asked to consider:

- **Wording issues** (confusing capabilities questions, proofreading changes, etc.)
- **Possible duplicates** (or opportunities to combine questions)
- **Opportunities for rearrangement** (e.g. moving questions between Facings or Topics)
- **Gaps in the model** (propose 'Missing Questions' in a given Topic and/or new Topics)

The workshop sessions were arranged as below:

9:30	9:50	Welcome, Introductions, and Goals for Today
9:50	10:45	Context, Setting up Breakouts, Institutional Profile review
10:45	11:00	<i>Coffee Break</i>
11:00	12:15	Breakout 2 - Reviewing existing capabilities, prose, etc.
12:15	1:15	<i>Lunch</i>
1:15	2:30	Breakout 3 - What's missing in the model?
2:30	2:50	<i>Networking Break</i>

2:50	4:05	Breakout 4 - Model and Portal Effectiveness
4:05	4:20	Wrap up and Next steps

Following context-setting presentations in the first session, participants across the entire room were invited to share general feedback, which included a number of usability enhancements to the new Model startup process, corresponding changes to the documentation, and others which the working group has since taken on for near-term development. Breakouts 2 and 3 focused specifically on the content of capabilities reflected in the Model's questions, with participants raising several content areas that could be addressed across facings (e.g. AI- and quantum-specific capabilities, cybersecurity and regulated data components, capabilities serving education-specific needs for RCD resources, etc.). A final breakout asked for considerations of the overall organization of the Model and other aspects of usability for the model and data visualization/benchmarking capabilities in the portal. Breakout groups (and sometimes facilitators) took notes in Google Documents for easy post-workshop review and annotation of proposed changes, by the Capabilities Model working group.

Workshop Facilitators

- **Patrick Schmitz**, Semper Cogito and Internet2 (contract); CaRCC Capabilities Model co-Chair, Logistics Group, Strategy- and Policy-Facing Steering Committee
- **Lauren Michael**, Internet2; CaRCC Capabilities Model co-Chair, Logistics co-Chair, People Network co-Coordinator, RCD Professionalization Working Group, Capabilities Model Working Group, Data-Facing Track Steering Committee
- **John Hicks**, Internet2; Capabilities Model Working Group

Key Takeaways

Upon reviewing the 'homework' documents and breakout group notes, the working group identified that proposed changes to Model content fall into several categories:

- **Immediate implementation** - Simple proofreading and wording adjustments that require no further review
- **Context-dependent revisions** - Wording changes that need consideration within their specific facing and topic area
- **Structural modifications** - Question additions, removals, or consolidations that impact the overall Model structure
- **Emerging topic additions** - New questions addressing yet-unrepresented or emerging capabilities (fewer than a dozen serious candidates identified)

Workshop attendees have already expressed interest in forming facing-specific focus groups to evaluate these changes within the framework of three key priorities: (1) maintaining the current overall facing structure, (2) incorporating emerging capabilities, and (3) keeping roughly the same total number of questions by identifying opportunities for removal or consolidation. The

working group also recognized that non-attendees may provide valuable contributions to these discussions.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Simpler changes - also including specifically-articulated enhancements to the upstart interface and content - are in the process of being implemented for a next point release, along with already known bug-fixes and corrections.

Based, in part, on specific feedback during the workshop, the working group is preparing to invite engaged workshop participants and other community members (who were not able to attend the workshop) to small facing-specific focus groups, based upon their apparent enthusiasm for different facings. Each group will consider the set of content changes to capabilities questions within their facing that the working group has distilled from workshop feedback. Multiple enthusiasts appear interested in more than one facing, so we recommend forming a subset of representatives from each group. These representatives can meet after the facing-specific groups to review all changes, confirm questions moved to new facings, and assess the scope of new questions on emerging topics like AI/quantum, cybersecurity, and education-specific use cases.

Feedback from the post-workshop survey and in person was largely positive, with some additional takeaways for future Capabilities Model work and other workshops. Attendees enjoyed the opportunity for focused work, smaller breakout groups, effective facilitation, and the importance of the work. Multiple survey respondents appreciated that the workshop conversations were a natural form of networking among peers with varying degrees of experience and deep thinking about CaRCC and the Capabilities Model. Given feedback requests to allow deeper consideration of subsets of questions between groups, the working group will organize follow-up work in bite-sized chunks among focused discussion groups, with some cross-pollination and summative coordination between groups (as described above).

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